

Human Capacity Building in Manufacturing Sector: A Factor to Industrial Growth in Nigeria.

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Abstract : Human ability is a major source of constraint to manufacturing industries in Nigeria. This paper therefore, discusses the importance of human influences on manufacturing and consequently to industrialisation and National development. In this paper, the development of manufacturing was anchored on two main factors; Infrastructural Capacity Development (ICD) and Human Capacity Development (HCD). However, a wider view was given to the HCD and the various contemporary human capacity issues militating against manufacturing in Nigeria. It went further to discuss various ways of acquiring and upgrading workers' skills and finally, suggestions were made on how to tackle the onerous human capacity issues in manufacturing.

Keywords : Manufacturing, Human, Capacity, Development, Innovation

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